

Pandemic in Retrospect: Students' Evaluation of Distance Education During the COVID-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

This study describes the distance learning experiences of university students in terms of their readiness, engagement, and performance amid the COVID-19 pandemic. It also examines the university's and the administration's support in attending to the academic and non-academic concerns of the students. Using a sequential explanatory design, the study utilized a quantitative online survey contextualized by qualitative methods such as key informant interviews and focus group discussions. The findings suggest the following: the students, in general, are equipped to manage distance education effectively, in terms of their gadgets, accessories, and internet connectivity; the remote learning mode engaged the students through the affordances brought by the learning platforms (VLE, MS Teams); and the students performed well in either major and general education subjects due in part to the support and performance of the teachers as well as the assistance of the university and the administration in laying down a framework for relevant teaching and learning. The students also demonstrated their preference for blended (50-50) classes, while it highlighted their concerns about mental health where it needed improvements. The study suggests that all forms of support are extended to optimize students' learning while in quarantine. The study hopes that the findings will inform the crafting of university online learning policies in the following semesters.

Keywords: Distance education, online learning, student performance and readiness, institutional support

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has compelled a radical shift towards alternative modes in all domains of human activity, such as in businesses and trade, health and well-being, traveling, and education and research, among others. In particular, the pandemic has significantly impacted the education sector everywhere in the world. Epidemiologists strongly recommended physical distancing protocols to slow its spread, which inadvertently led many educational institutions to partially or completely replace face-to-face classes with a distance learning approach.

Distance learning has enabled students to continue their studies during this global pandemic. Distance education, also referred to as distance learning, refers to the education of students who are not always physically present in school (Cleveland-Innes & Garrison, 2010; Holmberg, 2005). It is undertaken whenever a teacher teaches a student from a separate location. Allo (2020) estimates that nearly 300 million students worldwide have been affected by school adjustments during the COVID-19 pandemic.

As distance learning also involves online set-up, the quickness of the adoption of an online digital off-campus mode of teaching has raised concerns about the efficacy of online education and has prompted a probing of pedagogical issues (Pitroda, 2020; Gopinathan and Ramachandran, 2020). Although many educational institutions had some virtual learning platforms before the pandemic, this kind of distance learning differs from the one adopted as a response to COVID-19 distancing rules. This mode of education has been variously called “crisis distance education,” “emergency remote teaching,” or “transitional emergency model” (Lily et al., 2020; Hodges, 2020; Salama & Crosbie, 2020).

Whereas regular distance learning progresses with pedagogical and administrative frameworks, methods, tools, and processes (Basak et al., 2016; Hadullo et al., 2017), the sudden shift to online, off-campus education in unprecedented scale may lack the frameworks, tools, and other requisites suited to the pandemic situation. In context, the necessity of establishing acceptable frameworks for the different programs cannot

be overemphasized. Because of the immediacy of adaptation, several concerns on account of the digital divide, lack of inclusiveness, inequity, unaffordability, and value of online education were voiced (Aguilar, Lineses, Mazo & Ruben 2021); yet paradoxically, distance education is also purported as a panacea to these very issues (Kebritchi et al., 2017; Jena, 2020).

However, despite struggling with the rapid shift to online learning and the desire to return to face-to-face classes, as soon as physical distancing protocols are lifted, some institutions have attempted to leverage what they have learned from the transition to distance learning by expanding their online course offerings and/or deciding to retain the online set up for some courses. While many faculty and students found online courses less than ideal, others, forced into experiencing distance learning, may find themselves more attuned to the online modality and may go for distance learning if given a choice (Goldman & Karam, 2020).

In addition, some have called for universities to accept distance learning as an alternative to face-to-face classes even when distancing guidelines allow onsite resumption of classes (Taparia, 2020). Some reasons cited were the benefits the universities generate from using the internet to teach courses: saving campus spatial resources, expanding their reach to students from farther away, and so on (Aguilar & Torres, 2021; Lineses, 2021). Distance learning likewise is touted to offer benefits to students such as being more compatible with a work-related lifestyle, saving resources such as costs and time on commuting to campus, and attending universities with less regard to the location (Aguilar et al., 2021; Lineses, 2021). Towards these ends, the De La Salle University-Dasmarias (DLSU-D), a Catholic University, followed this distance learning route amid the pandemic.

One thing remains unclear whether students want to continue their distance learning when circumstances no longer require it. Universities may be tempted to pursue distance education on a large scale because the forced experience of online classes can make students more willing to take online courses. However, it would be a mistake to assume that they will simply. While some students may be willing to continue taking classes online,

others may prefer face-to-face classes. Thus, it would be helpful to understand the factors that influence students' views of distance education. This is the study's focal point: to articulate students' perception of online learning and the factors behind their approval or disapproval. This research provides useful information on these questions, and the results of this study will be a valuable resource for teaching modes in succeeding semesters.

Prior to the pandemic, as early as 2010, the university had courses that used a blended learning approach, relying much on the university's subscribed virtual learning environment (VLE) from NEO-LMS, dubbed as the Schoolbook (SB). This presupposes that for those who incorporated SB in their instruction, rethinking their methodologies and getting to know how to use different technologies in distance education may not have been very difficult. However, as intimated by an administrator of DLSU-D, many faculty members chose not to use the VLE in their classes prior to the pandemic. Hence, when the use of VLE was mandated during the pandemic, those new to it found that teaching students through remote teaching demanded establishing a learning relationship with the students and different preparation of the tasks, including different scaffoldings leading to independent learning, which they had to learn quickly. However, since online teaching offers a myriad of strategies, teachers can tailor-fit their classes to the needs of the students. Following this, it is important then to solicit the views of the students, as they are the recipients of the different modes of instruction during the pandemic period.

This study aims to describe the distance learning experiences viewed by university students during the quarantine period. The views of the students are deemed valuable in crafting class policies regarding online learning in view of the anticipated modes of instruction/teaching in the semesters following the pandemic. In particular, the study aims to answer the following research questions succinctly:

1. What are the attributes of the students in the university?
2. How do students rate their readiness for distance education in view of their internet connectivity, platform, and gadget usage?

3. What is the level of engagement and performance of the students in distance education?
4. How do students assess their learning based on the ratings they give to their teachers' performance, the delivery of classes, and their own efforts?
5. In what ways did the administration assist the students in their academic as well as non-academic concerns?
6. What is the preferred learning mode of the students in the coming semesters?

Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-method approach, particularly the sequential explanatory type. Quantitative data was first gathered, after which initial analysis was undertaken to generate important findings and insights. Qualitative methods were then conducted to contextualize the quantitative data, consisting of key informant interviews (KIIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs).

The quantitative findings in this study were facilitated through an online survey using Google Forms for DLSU-D students in July 2022. The online medium was adopted because of its suitability in collecting required information as well as its wide outreach at a time when physical interactions have been constrained due to the pandemic. Watson and Lupton (2022) affirm that gathering data through digital means can be an acceptable method as it also allows for rich data to be gathered, and during distancing protocols, it is part of adaptive strategies (Aguilar et al., 2021).

The questions elicited perceptual information on aspects of distance education, IT/online platforms and tools, the efficacy of online teaching-learning, and blended learning trajectory. Moreover, questions on their own assessment of instruction in major and general education subjects, and delivery by instructor were also included.

The locale of this study is De La Salle University-Dasmarias (DLSU-D), which has a total student population of 11,165 (as of 2022) spread over its seven colleges: College of Business Administration (CBA), College of Science (COS), College of Engineering, Architecture, and

Technology (CEAT), College of Liberal Arts and Communication (CLAC), College of Tourism and Hospitality Management (CTHM), College of Criminology and Justice Education (CCJE) and the College of Education (COE).

The participants of the study were mostly second-year and third-year students. It can be remembered that when the distancing protocols were imposed in March 2020, the sophomore students were then first-year students in their second semester of SY 2020-2021. Likewise, the third-year students were then sophomores, also in the middle of the second semester of classes. Hence, most had experienced the onsite classes inside the campus. Also, as shown in Table 1, more than half of the respondents came from the College of Liberal Arts and Communication (CLAC), comprising 57.7 %.

Table 1. The Survey Sample

Student information	Frequency	Percentage
College		
CLAC	71	57.7
CIHM	6	6
CSCS	1	.8
CBA	23	18.7
COE	20	16.3
CEAT	2	1.6
Year Level		
1	19	15.4
2	51	41.5
3	49	39.8
4	4	3.3
Total	123	100

The initial analysis of the quantitative findings prompted the conduct of key informant interviews among student leaders, regular students, and administrators to understand the implications of the figures generated further. FGDs among students were also conducted to enrich the findings.

Results and Discussion

This section is divided into five (5) parts as articulated in the research problems: attributes of the students, engagement and performance in distance education, assessment of learning,

institutional support, and students' preference of learning modality.

Attributes of the Students

A total of 123 university students participated in this study. As Table 2 shows, most of the respondents are female, consisting of 65% and within the age range of 19 to 22 ($\bar{X} = 20.7$). It can be noted that three (3) respondents were based abroad while 114 (84.5%) live in the Philippine province of Cavite, of which 47 students reside in the City of Dasmariñas, where DLSU-D is located.

Table 2. Background of the Respondents

Demographic	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	35	28.5
Female	80	65
LGBTQA	7	5.7
No response	1	.8
Age		
19-20	60	48.8
21-22	54	43.9
23 and above	8	7.3
$\bar{X} = 20.7$		
Residence		
Within Dasmariñas	47	38.2
Within Cavite	57	46.3
Within the Philippines	16	13
Abroad	3	2.4

The change in the learning environment during the COVID-19 lockdown period was abrupt, where everyone, including students, had to stay home, thereby rendering the house as a learning space. Students and teachers not used to utilizing a learning management system (LMS) were forced to use this educational technology to cope with the present learning context, as this provides the necessary structure for facilitating online learning (Moodley et al., 2022). The role of educational institutions is to provide this structure (Belhaj, 2022), without which remote or distance learning cannot proceed.

In the case of DLSU-D, the Schoolbook has been used in instruction but was not compulsory prior to the pandemic. The use of the platform varied among colleges and departments. Some of

them utilized SB in uploading reading materials, and others were limited to the use of the gradebook application for recording assessments. COVID-19 compelled the use of LMS as it has become the most important channel for creating a learning environment for students (Alturki & Aldraiweesh, 2021).

By using the LMS, students easily access the materials or modules. It must be noted that “learning is effectively achieved when the appropriate instructional materials are used for the right purpose during the process, and the students can get available advantages of material (Belhaj, 2022).

Learning experience using LMS requires electronic devices such as laptops or cellphones. In this study, 74.8% of the respondents have their own personal laptop or desktop; and 116 or 94.3% have their own WIFI or broadband, which they rated generally as reliable. Only a handful, 5.7%, use mobile data. This means that almost all, if not most, students enrolled in DLSU-D have access to online learning during the pandemic.

However, having several family members using the internet may potentially affect its connectivity and speed. Even though students have many concerns about poor internet connection, they do not have any issues adapting to online platforms, such as the marriage between Schoolbook and MS Teams. Though there are several internet users at home, students still see the advantages of online learning and the flexibility of learning (Tomic et al., 2022).

Table 3 shows that the internet is shared at home among family members, with an average of 4.5. Fifty (50) respondents, or 40.8%, claimed that more than 5 use the internet at home, while 25% or 31 had three internet users. According to TRAFICOM (n.d.), a Finnish Transport and Communication Agency, multiple factors affect the speed and quality of internet connectivity, and this includes using multiple services, simultaneously using several gadgets, and having several people logged on to the network at once.

Table 3. Frequency of Internet Users at Home

Number of Users at Home	Frequency	Percentage
1	10	8.1
2	10	8.1
3	31	25.2
4	19	15.4
5 and above	50	40.8
No response	3	2.4
x̄ number of users: 4.5		

In terms of gadgets used for synchronous and asynchronous classes, more than half (67%) considered their primary gadgets and accessories, such as microphones, headsets, and cameras, in good condition and working well. This means that during the pandemic when students were at home, their gadgets enabled the learning process to continue. Notwithstanding the unprecedented health conditions brought by COVID-19, the academe effectually coped by utilizing online learning platforms (Belhaj, 2022). The unpleasant health condition caused by COVID-19 has not hindered learning. Though there have been technical concerns in the conduct of online classes, learning has continued, and it has built and enhanced specific knowledge and skills for learners (Kumar & Ganesh, 2022).

Despite the number of users of WIFI at home, the respondents deemed the quality of their internet connectivity as very functional ($\bar{x} = 3.77$ / high). Only one (.8%) respondent claimed to have the least reliable and stable connectivity at home. This presupposes that relative to the quality of the internet, students could participate effectively in online learning using services requiring substantive bandwidth like video calling, most often done during synchronous classes, and downloading materials from their VLE. Video conferencing is also a virtual communication channel and dialogue between a teacher and his or her students and/or among the students. Downloading materials helps students read and study modules at their own pace. In this learning context, students become more aware of their responsibility in the learning process.

Engagement and Performance in Distance Education

Before the pandemic, when classes were normally onsite, students often did not know their classmates at the beginning of the school year. They usually get to know each other as the semester progresses through class interaction. During the pandemic, however, the physical distancing protocols resulting from remote learning made building a sense of community within the class more difficult. Presumably, seeing each other, albeit on-screen, can enhance presence and contribute to better engagement amongst and between students and teachers during synchronous class. The use of a camera is a very important tool for boosting class interaction. This study explored this area.

As shown in Figure 3, 89 (72.4%) of the students turned on their cameras when called upon by their professors during synchronous meetings. However, 29 (23.6%) turned off their cameras most of the time and 3 (2.4%) never turned them on. Thus, often, students only see blank squares or pictures of their classmates on-screen during synchronous classes. This suggests that students, if given the choice, do not prefer to turn on their cameras during synchronous meetings.

Why do students turn off their cameras most of the time? In a study conducted by Castelli and Sarvacy (2020), a major reason was the concern for their appearance. If they turn on their cameras, they must tidy themselves, wear appropriate attire even at home, and look presentable, to name a few. The next most frequently cited reason is their unease when other family members are seen in the background because some students do not have their private space for synchronous meetings. They attend classes in their living room or dining rooms, where other family members normally spend time together. Finally, others think it is the norm since everyone has their cameras turned off.

Teachers, however, are expected to have their cameras turned on for the whole duration of the synchronous meeting. Having cameras turned on establishes an instructor’s presence and a connection between the teacher and the students. This also increases levels of engagement and tells the students that their teacher is ready and focused on the work ahead.

However, the respondents of this study seem to disagree with this assumption.

As shown in Figure 4, only 40 (32.5%) students prefer that their teacher's camera is turned on all the time during their synchronous meetings. Moreover, 37 (30.1%) students want it only open when speaking, and 15 (12.2%) prefer audio only during synchronous meetings. Lastly, 29 (24%) students expressed that whether they see their teacher on screen does not matter.

Some practical reasons for this seeming apathy for on-cam teaching included ease in multi-tasking and ubiquitous learning. Since they are learning remotely, when the teacher's camera is off, they can do other things like household chores, run errands, or even read other lessons, especially when an exam is given in the next class. Some are even able to "attend" two meetings at once.

Other students cited the primacy of teaching style. As one student succinctly explained,

"There are professors that still efficiently and excellently deliver their lectures without their cameras open. I think the professors should not be obligated to open their cameras if they are not comfortable, feeling well, or if their internet is bad."

This indifference to on-cam presence is seconded by another who expressed that,

"...There are effective teachers that turn off their cameras but can actually teach, educate and promote class participation (even if students have their cameras off)."

This emergent issue of why students seem to prefer an off-cam teacher has been explored in recent studies on video conferencing fatigue (Salim et al., 2022). Although the transition to synchronous classes has worked well for some, others feel burdened. Others find relief in seeing their teacher and classmates virtually as it offers a sense of social connection and engagement they would not otherwise get studying remotely.

The shift has been a challenge for others, who have reported discomfort and fatigue having to sit in place for long periods of time and focus on the detached communication portal in front of them. Videoconference fatigue is "a feeling of exhaustion caused by sustained attention during

videoconferences..." (Bennett et al., 2021). This leads to the feeling of being drained. According to Shockley (2021), "We knew people had the perception that Zoom meetings were leading to fatigue, but we didn't know what about those meetings was the problem. Our study revealed that there is something about the camera being on that causes people to feel drained and lack energy." As such, when the teacher's camera is turned on for the duration of the meeting, the students assume that they, too, need to focus and look at the screen at the same time the teacher faces them, which causes fatigue.

Another important activity that enhances engagement is recitation during synchronous meetings. It encourages real-time participation and interaction. Students were asked about their experience of this.

Table 4. Recitation Frequency

Frequency of Recitation	Frequency	Percentage
More than once during synchronous class	19	15.4
At least once during synchronous class	53	43.1
Rarely	48	39.0
No response	3	2.4

As shown in Table 4, only 19 or 15.4 % recite more than once, 53/ 43.1 % recite at least once during synchronous meetings, while 48 or 39.0 % rarely recite. The respondents of this study do not seem to think that recitation is an integral part of a class, even more so in an online setting when presence and engagement are challenging.

Participation in all teaching and learning environments is essential as it reinforces the concepts taught in class, and learning authentically occurs, especially when "students play a large role in directing the flow of topics and ideas" (Nystrand & Gamoran, 1990). While students absorb information from traditional lectures and readings, learners can also benefit from additional teaching models such as discussion-based instruction, recitation, etc. However, Moneva (2020) cautions

that oral recitation may bring about anxiety, which could embolden students to skip class if they are not ready for an announced graded recitation.

A sophomore suggests one strategy to foster participation without creating anxiety is by conducting a survey. As narrated, in their Microsoft Teams, their teacher created polls to check in with students and assess whether they are reaching a shared level of understanding, such as a true-or-false question at the beginning of class drawn from the previous lesson. Even if some students give wrong answers, it most often leads to discussing what topics they are still struggling with.

In the FGDs, students collectively observed that active learning in an online, synchronous lesson can feel daunting but essential. The survey gives more information on the area of participation in group work.

Online learning can leave students feeling lonely and disengaged. Unlike the ‘normal’ onsite classes, students can lack a sense of belonging when attending classes remotely because they cannot get to know their teachers and classmates. Incorporating group activities and projects into online classes can help increase engagement and a sense of belonging.

Table 5. Group Activity Participation

Participation in Group Activity/project	Frequency	Percentage
Highly participative	70	56.9
Participative	38	30.9
Moderately participative	9	7.3
Only a bit, hard to collab	4	3.3
None, better on my own	2	1.6

As shown in Table 5, 70 or 56.9 % are highly participative in group activities during synchronous meetings. Four students, or 3.3 %, found it hard to collaborate, and two, or 1.6 %, did not participate.

During the team assessment, group projects are given in SB, where the class is divided into groups. In the team assessment, each group has its own pages or working hubs where they communicate and collaborate. During synchronous class meetings, some classes used the breakout rooms feature in MS Teams. In the breakout rooms,

the students were placed into smaller groups, and they worked together on finding a solution to a problem. They went back into the plenary and presented their solution. The high percentage of highly participative students in group activities shows that they see the value of working together, even in an online setting. Steve Greenlaw, a professor of economics at the University of Mary Washington, said, “One of the things that I try to do is provide the same amount of interactivity in the teaching and learning online as I do face-to-face. I think that’s how learning happens best.” (Lieberman, 2018)

Key informant interviews with administrators elaborate on this matter. At the start of the full remote learning mode, some questions were considered in depth as they can crucially impact the successful online migration: What do we want learners to know and be able to do, and what platform can best help them attain these learning goals? Virtual learning platforms have enabled the synchronous and asynchronous interactions between faculty-students and students-students, and this has led to the adoption of Schoolbook and Microsoft Teams as its virtual learning platforms in DLSU-D (Lineses, 2021).

Table 6. Most Effective Platforms

Most Effective Platforms	Frequency	Percentage
Schoolbook	22	17.9
Teams	13	10.6
Schoolbook and Teams	66	53.7
Messenger	17	13.8
No response	5	4.1

As shown in Table 6, 66 or 53.7 % considered the Schoolbook and MS Teams as the most effective platforms. Seventeen (17) or 13.8 % considered Messenger of Facebook as an effective platform for synchronous meetings.

MS Teams has improved a lot with its features during the pandemic. More and more teachers and educators fall back on its services to host virtual class meetings, webinars, and conferences. Some of the services used during synchronous meetings are screen sharing, sharing files with colleagues and working on them together in real-time, unlimited chat, and together mode. It has been our platform for synchronous meetings.

The Schoolbook is where the teachers upload their lesson materials and assessments. Messaging, chat, and group pages are just some features that promote student communication and collaboration. Gamification is one feature in SB that is viewed positively by students. “Gamifying online classes promotes an active learning environment that ensures students’ engagement despite the restricted virtual interaction they have with their teachers and classmates.” (Acal & Ruben, 2021).

Though not prescribed by the university, some teachers use Messenger as a learning platform. It appears to have advantages such as easy interaction, comfort in getting information, easy to use and share information, while being too open to the public is seen as a disadvantage (Hassan, 2014). Data security is the main reason the use of Messenger as a learning platform is not allowed. Convenience must not be chosen over security with online platforms.

Assessment of Learning

In an FGD among graduating students on how their learning has been affected by the disruptions created by the pandemic, the prevailing notion is the heroic efforts of students to learn and educators to teach in the incredibly trying times, sustaining the academic tasks. The survey results echo this finding.

Table 7. Quality of Synchronous Classes

Type of Subject	Mean	Interpretation
Major Subjects	3.80	High
General Education Subjects	3.59	High
Overall \bar{x}	3.69	High

As shown in Table 7, the students believed that the quality of synchronous classes in the university is high ($\bar{X}=3.69$) for both major and general education subjects. While the two types of subjects are generally held the same by the students, it is noted that the quality of synchronous instruction in major subjects is higher ($\bar{X}=3.80$) than in general education subjects ($\bar{X}=3.59$).

The same percentage of students (36.6%) regarded synchronous instruction for both major

and general education subjects as “very good”. However, a quarter of the respondents (25.2%) considered the classes to be better in major subjects than in general education (16.3%).

This implies that the respondents preferred how instruction is done in major subjects over the general education subjects. Students admit that they exert more effort to learn in their major field of concentration and are more concerned about their grades here compared to the general education subjects. In part, the students are better prepared in their major subjects, and this perhaps explains why their assessment scores are higher.

Table 8. Performance of Teachers

Type of Subject	Mean	Interpretation
Major Subjects	4.13	High
General Education Subjects	3.93	High
Overall \bar{x}	4.03	High

Table 8 presents the performance of teachers in both major and general education subjects. The students generally perceived their teachers to be very good ($\bar{X}=4.03$) in the conduct of synchronous classes. However, the students regarded their teachers in major subjects to be relatively “better” ($\bar{X}=4.13$) than those teachers in general education ($\bar{X}=3.93$) subjects.

Most of the students regarded their teachers’ performance in both major and general education subjects as “very good”, with 42.3% and 46.3%, respectively. However, a third of the students (36.6%) held that their teachers performed “excellent” in major subjects compared to those in general education, with only just a quarter (25.2%).

The higher rating given to teachers of major subjects may be partly due to their familiarity with the topics and the teacher’s handling, as compared to the general education teachers. The different major subjects share theories and methodologies, and many subjects build from previous subjects, allowing for learning continuity. This resonates with Shell and Soh (2013), who explained further that students perceive major courses to give the most important preparation for skills and training for their future careers compared to non-major

courses. Hence, students naturally tend to study more seriously in their major courses and listen more attentively to their teachers.

Table 9. Learning and Teaching During Quarantine Period

Key Areas	Mean	Interpretation
Personal Performance	3.67	High
Coping with Academic Requirements	4.05	High
Extensiveness of Personal Learning	3.54	High
Effectiveness of Learning and Teaching	3.73	High
Overall \bar{x}	3.75	High

As seen in Table 9, the respondents rated some key areas in learning and teaching during the quarantine period. These areas include the students' personal performance, their coping with academic requirements, the extensiveness of their personal learning, and the effectiveness of online learning and teaching in general. The students mainly rated the said areas to be "very good" ($\bar{X}=3.75$).

Almost half (43.1%) of the students perceived their personal performance to be "just okay", a third thought it to be "very good" (33.3%), and a fifth (19.5%) thought themselves to be "excellent". On average, the respondents deemed their performance to be "High" ($\bar{X}=3.67$).

In terms of coping with academic requirements, most (37.5%) regarded it to be "good", many (35.8%) admittedly were able to cope "very much", and more than a quarter (26.8%) just simply "cannot tell". The students viewed their coping with requirements as "high" ($\bar{X}=4.05$).

As to the extensiveness of personal learning, many students believed their learning to be "good" (39%) and "okay" (35%); while only a few (14.6%) thought the extent to be "very much". The students considered the extensiveness of their learning to be "high" ($\bar{X}=3.54$).

In relation to the effectiveness of learning and teaching, around half of the students (48.8%) perceived it to be "Effective". While almost a fifth (17.1%) thought learning and teaching to be "very

effective", more than a quarter (26.8%) admitted they "cannot tell". In general, the respondents believed the extent of learning and teaching during the quarantine period to be "high" ($\bar{X}=3.73$).

From the above, the cumulative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on students' academic achievement seems to be acceptable altogether, given the overall rating of "high". However, it is still interesting to find out why the score did not reach "very high".

On Institutional Support

There are no perfect systems, especially newly established ones such as the online learning at DLSU-D. The university can only try to offer the best possible educational experience, but the students may encounter challenges, concerns, and technical difficulties along the way. As such, the university must have available mechanisms to support whenever needed. These mechanisms include policies and guidelines on the conduct of online classes; creative programs and activities designed to make online learning effective; availability of the faculty to address the questions and concerns of the students; readiness of the student welfare offices to respond to the psycho-emotional needs of the students; and the accessibility of staff to deal with technical difficulties.

Table 10 presents the extent of institutional support provided to the students during the quarantine period. The support included those from the administration and the faculty and the technical and psycho-emotional support systems. Overall, the students regarded the support extended to them as "high" ($\bar{X}=3.94$).

Table 10. Institutional Support

Support Areas	Mean	Interpretation
Support from Administration	3.94	High
Support from Faculty	3.90	High
Technical Support	3.69	High
Psycho-emotional Support	3.86	High
Overall \bar{X}	3.85	High

Support from Administration

When the respondents were asked about the support given by the administration, the findings suggest that they were “highly satisfied” ($\bar{x}=3.94$) with the way the administration managed the online learning in the university. Most students (41.5%) “agreed” that the administration exerted evident efforts in carrying out effective online learning classes. Roughly more than a quarter “strongly agreed” (28.5%), though others (26.8%) seemed to be “neutral” about the support given by the administration.

One factor in the success of online learning is how teaching-learning is carried out. In the case of DLSU-D, online learning is conducted asynchronously and synchronously. Asynchronously, modules are designed and published in its subscribed VLE called Schoolbook; synchronously, interactive discussions are conducted via Microsoft Teams. To ensure smooth educational experiences for the teachers and students, the administration conducted regular training and orientations on the use of Schoolbooks and Microsoft Teams.

Another aspect that may have contributed to the perceived satisfaction in the way the administration managed online learning in the university is the implementation of the Implementing Rules and Regulations of the Care-Center Model of Learning (IRR), the framework by which the remote teaching and learning during the pandemic was facilitated. Among others, the IRR provides the policies and guidelines on how online classes should be carried out in both synchronous and asynchronous sessions; the design of syllabi and modules; the guidelines for giving assessments; and the provision on self-care, which are all designed to see to it that students are not overly burdened with activities and to make their online engagement as bearable and meaningful as possible. In fact, the IRR has undergone several revisions to address student concerns in the conduct of previous online classes.

Support from Faculty

As regards the support extended by the faculty members, the results suggest that they were “highly satisfied” ($\bar{X}=3.90$) with how they managed the classes. Most students (39.8%) agreed

that their teachers were supportive and readily available to them, which means more than a third of the respondents regarded the support of their teachers more than satisfactory. Many “strongly agreed” (29.3%), while less than a quarter (23.6%) were “neutral” to the support and availability of the teachers. This represents little more than 7% who were unsatisfied with the way the faculty handled student concerns.

As online learning ushers a dialogue between the faculty and the students, it is a must that the former is always available, ready, and willing to respond to questions and concerns, especially in times when lessons and instructions are not readily understood. Nay, they must exhibit proficiency in the utilization of the learning platforms used in the delivery of the lessons so that they can readily respond to academic inquiries.

Although generally satisfactory, one student leader intimated that communication with their teachers is admittedly an area in the online set-up that was challenging:

“The only difficult part was when trying to get in contact with professors since some of them just straight-up ignore e-mails, answering no would have been better, at least you know they read your letter. Many of my blockmates have the same experience.”

Technical Support

In terms of technical support, the respondents expressed High satisfaction ($\bar{X} = 3.69$) with the way the university extended support to the students. Most of the students “highly” (39.8%) believed that the school’s technical support was available, prompt, and easily accessible through calls, chats, and emails. While some thought the support was “very high” (21.1%), there were more who appeared “Neutral” (27.6%) to it, while a few (10.4%) even were dissatisfied with the support system.

While educational technologies have been around for some decades now, the use of virtual learning platforms such as NEO-LMS and Microsoft Teams is relatively new. The use of VLE was only intensified during the pandemic when educational institutions were constrained to implement a

full online learning modality. Because of this, proficiency in the use of educational platforms is not to be immediately expected from the faculty and students, especially from those who refused to use them in the beginning. Even those who manage the learning platform have a hard time figuring out some technical difficulties.

Psycho-emotional Support

Based on interviews, students have encountered various online learning-related problems such as (a) technical difficulties, (b) problems in communication, (c) inability to focus on studies due to distractions, (d) incompatibility between the teaching approach and the learning styles of the students; and worst (e) mental health problems.

In terms of psycho-emotional support, the students gave the university high satisfaction rating ($\bar{X} = 3.86$). The respondents recognized the efforts of the university in addressing their mental health needs, although they also recognized that much can still be improved in this area, as almost a fifth (18.7%) thought that only a little was done, while a considerable 6.5% indicated that the school had barely considered this concern.

Cognizant of the fact that some students suffer from mental health concerns, the university provided mechanisms by which students would be able to cope with the demands of online learning. Some of them are as follows: a) provision of the self-care week and self-care hub; (b) availability and accessibility of guidance counselors in cases when students need their services; (c) accompaniment activities by formation offices; and (d) extra-curricular activities sponsored by various offices and student organizations in the university. All are meant to make the online learning of students bearable and meaningful.

Nonetheless, the students still experienced psycho-emotional difficulties. A staggering 95.1% of the respondents expressed that they had experienced mental health problems at some time during the quarantine period. A quarter of the respondents (25.2%) admitted mental health has been a concern for them “all the time”; a fifth of them experienced it “most of the time” (21.1%), and

almost the same number have experienced it “many times” (19.5%).

The demands of academics, on top of the familial and existential concerns that the students encounter in the face of the uncertainty brought about by the pandemic, have taken a toll on the mental health of many students. One can just imagine how difficult it is for students to fulfill their academic requirements while dealing with mental health concerns.

Overall, the students are more than satisfied with the administrative, faculty, technical, and psycho-emotional support provided by the university, which suggests that the university was able to handle their concerns very well. In fact, the students rated the support extended by the university as High ($\bar{X} = 3.85$). Most of them considered the support acceptable (39%), many indicated very well (37.4%), and some even indicated excellent (15.4%).

Preferred Learning Mode in the Coming Semesters

After experiencing full online learning for two years, considering its advantages and disadvantages, students were asked about the mode of learning they preferred for the coming semesters. Figure 10 indicates that a) the greatest number of students preferred a blend of onsite and online learning (50-50); b) followed by enriched online (mostly online and a few onsite) at 20.3%; then full onsite at 17.1%; and full online at 15.4%.

Between full online and full onsite modes of learning, the respondents preferred the latter,

though with a small margin of 2%. This means that despite the advantages brought about by online classes, the respondents still preferred onsite sessions, presumably because of the challenges inherent to remote learning, as pointed out by a senior student:

“Overall participation can be deemed as a challenge during online engagements. It is difficult to build connections through the screens and likewise, focus our attention since attending online classes can be distracting.”

While the respondents found full online learning highly effective (please see Table No. 8), they did not recommend it as the mode of learning in the coming semesters. As Figure No. 10 shows, full online learning ranks last among the five choices.

It is interesting to note that the respondents did not agree with the conduct of either full online class or full onsite class. This suggests the respondents' awareness of the disadvantages of each mode of learning, which the other mode of learning may complement. Having experienced both modes of learning, the respondents may have realized that returning to the traditional mode of learning is no longer practical, as the “egg of online learning had already been hatched”.

While more than the majority of the respondents agreed that online learning at DLSU-D is highly effective, in what sense it is highly effective is not clear. Online learning may be said to be effective when the students have achieved the learning outcomes set for the course when they have learned what they ought to in the course. However, in the interview with the respondents, the effectiveness of online learning is not one reason why some preferred online classes for the succeeding semesters. When asked about the best feature of online classes, the respondents cited the following reasons, which have nothing to do with effectiveness of learning, to wit: (a) they are able to save money in the sense that they do not have to go to school in order to learn; (b) they are able to maximize time for they can study and do other things at the same time; (c) it offers flexibility in time and space in the sense that they can study at their pace at any place; and (d) they have more time for their families.

Despite the difficulties and challenges confronted by the students in online learning, students have realized the advantages brought about by online learning. In interviews with the students, they cited the following as the reasons why they preferred online classes to continue even though onsite classes may already be conducted: (a) online learning is the demand of the 21st century; (b) the social world has already changed to which education should adapt; (c) the internet has made the world interconnected which makes education beyond borders possible; and (d) with the availability of creative teaching tools online, technological change has made possible teaching and learning dynamic.

Given above, as Figure No. 10 clearly shows, the pandemic has ushered a new mode of learning which combines the indispensability of face-to-face interaction and the practicality of online learning. This may be called hybrid learning modalities, which are either blended learning (50% onsite and 50% online) or enriched virtual learning (more online learning than onsite).

Conclusions

The pandemic certainly tested students' capacity to adjust to a difficult disruption brought about by the sudden switch to remote learning, which required massive adjustment to one's behaviors, thoughts, and feelings in handling their academic and personal lives.

The students, in general, are equipped to effectively manage distance education in terms of their gadgets, accessories, and internet connectivity. With a fully functioning VLE that the university subscribed to, distance education was enabled during the period of physical distancing protocols. From the students' point of view, the remote mode did not prevent engagement through online strategies afforded by the Schoolbook (the VLE) and MS Teams. Performance-wise, the students did well in their major and general education subjects, perhaps in part due to the good performance of their teachers in both major and general education subjects, as they rated.

The university was able to assist the students

in their academic and non-academic concerns. Apart from the teachers, the administration extended support in the form of technical assistance and psycho-emotional support systems. Primarily, the administration provided not only collective discussion, training, and orientations through the CILP but, even more so, the framework of the Care-Centered Model of Learning and the implementing rules and regulations thereof, which advanced the use of the VLE in continuing instruction despite pandemic.

Moreover, the autonomy the students have over their learning processes was recognized by the students. Consistently, though, when the respondents were asked why they preferred that online classes continue, the reasons given did not include the effectiveness of online classes. Students likewise acknowledged the difficulties of remote learning and the advantages of the onsite classes, which explains their preference for 50-50 onsite and online classes.

From there, it can be assumed that the support from the family by way of the provision of gadgets and connectivity, support from teachers through the facilitation of remote teaching, and institutional support through the provision of online education platforms have been enough to merit students' high satisfaction of online learning in DLSU-D. The need for improvement can be addressed in the non-academic areas, such as mental health concerns.

Recommendations

In view of the conclusions arrived at in this study, several recommendations on a myriad of concerns on distance education are advanced.

1. The conduct of a follow-up study on the effectiveness of online learning is crucial, particularly in terms of its operationalization. It is interesting to know their views of the indicators of effectiveness in the context of distance education, as this has implications for pedagogy.
2. As the students preferred a hybrid learning modality for the coming semesters, the university should come up with a pedagogical framework (including infrastructures and systems and their

accompanying guidelines) in accordance with which it shall be implemented in view of the goal of achieving effective and meaningful educational experiences for both the faculty and students. Some creative strategies in hybrid learning that the university may explore include clustering classes and team teaching, among others.

3. While the pandemic may be considered a major factor contributing to the mental health problems of the students, the study intimated that academic structures and processes are likewise instrumental to it. It is a must for the university to inquire more deeply about the psycho-emotional and existential condition of the students. Conducting an in-depth study on the mental health of the students, particularly in the areas of forging social connections, managing distractions, and coping with pressure, among others, can aid in creating effective mental health programs.

4. The university must continue to extend technical support to teachers and students who have experienced difficulties in connectivity and setting up learning platforms. A readily available staff must be provided for this purpose to respond promptly to the technical concerns of teachers and students.

5. To forge "presence" in the conduct of online classes, turning on the camera for both teachers and students should be imperative. However, the usage must be within the bounds of reason and practicality as "zoom fatigue" is also found to be real, as expressed by the students who prefer webcams but not all the time. Notwithstanding the issues of bandwidth, the findings propose to build a culture of webcams and their use for students at the beginning, the end, and during the times when they speak or recite and for the teachers for most of the time, save when they are doing other activities during online classes, e.g., breakout, clip viewing, etc.

6. Due to methodological limitations, the study further recommends extending the study and the sampling to more students and including teachers to generate more varied information that would bolster and represent the study's findings.

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